

Frontiers of Biogeography; Phylogeny and the historical biogeography to assess the role of environment and altitude in the diversification of Ceratophryidae (Anura: Hyloidea) frogs in South America; Arjen A.W. van der Kamp, H. Mauricio Ortega-Andrade.

Chacophrys pierottii

<https://www.shutterstock.com/es/image-photo/chaco-horned-frog-chacophrys-pierottii1208803807>

Lepidobatrachus asper

<https://www.biodiversidadfaunacordoba.com/anfibios-escuerzo-salinero.html>

Bonino, E. E. et al. 2012. La Conservación de la Fauna en Córdoba [CD Rom] 1^a. Ed. Facultad de Ciencias Exactas Físicas y Naturales, Universidad Nacional de Córdoba. Córdoba. ISBN e-book 978-950-33-0996-4

Lepidobatrachus laevis

<https://www.biodiversidadfaunacordoba.com/anfibios-escuerzo-salinero.html>

Lepidobatrachus llanensis

<https://www.naturalista.mx/taxa/23231-Lepidobatrachus-llanensis>

Ceratophrys cornuta

<https://bioweb.bio/galeria/Foto/Ceratophrys%20cornuta/Fotos/1267>

Ceratophrys calcarata

<https://www.batrachia.com/orden-anura/ceratophryidae-2-spp/ceratophrys-calcarata/>

Ceratophrys stolzmanni

<https://amphibiaweb.org/species/5724>

Ceratophrys ornata

<https://www.alamy.es/horned-frog-argentino-ceratophrys-ornata-contr-a-el-fondoblanco-image67306911.html?imageid=E5A9F8C7-C403-49AE-BC9C88A5D5E398EB&p=84959&pn=1&searchId=2605b27e80ffa9272204f8d9da9aae4&searchtype=0>

Ceratophrys cranwelli

<https://www.istockphoto.com/es/search/2/image?phrase=Ceratophrys%20cranwelli>

Ceratophrys joazeirensis

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Adult-Ceratophrys-joazeirensis-collected-in-SantaMaria-Municipality-showing-the_fig3_290472141/actions#reference

On the natural history of the Caatinga Horned Frog, *Ceratophrys joazeirensis* (Anura: Ceratophryidae), a poorly known species of northeastern Brazil - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Adult-Ceratophrysjoazeirensis-collected-in-Santa-Maria-Municipality-showing-the_fig3_290472141 [accessed 11 Jul, 2023]

Ceratophrys aurita

<https://www.gbif.org/es/occurrence/3858798838>